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Review Article

From Tradition to Modern Medicine: Investigating the Pharmacological Benefits of Curry Leaves.

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ABSTRACT

Murraya koenigii (Curry Leaves/Kadhi Patta/Mitha Nimba/Giri Nimba) is a native of India and is found almost everywhere in the Except very high level of Himalayas mostly Indian subcontinent. Herbal drugs, low cost and having no side effect, have been widely used in many diseases since ancient time. Curry leaf has a very important place in traditional Ayurveda medicine. Part of the leaves, roots and all parts of a small deciduous shrub are rich in medicinal properties and nutrition which can be an industrial crop in future. It is rich in bioactive compounds have antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and hepatoprotective properties. They also aid digestion, help regulate cholesterol levels, and support good metabolic health.

INTRODUCTION

“Nature Is The Best Way To Heal.” Medicinal herbs and the use of natural folk medicine has been known in every culture around the world for centuries. Knowing the actual health benefits of these remedies doctors and researchers are getting increasingly interested in this field. The main benefits of using medicinal plants for therapeutic purposes across different diseases are believed to be their safety, as well as their ease of access, cost-effectiveness and efficacy [1]. Curry leaves, scientifically known as *Murraya koenigii*, are fragrant leaves frequently used in Indian and other

South Asian cooking. They are typically added to flavor curries, chutneys, vegetables, and drinks. In Sanskrit, *Murraya koenigii* Spreng is referred to as "Surabhinimba" and is part of the Rutaceae family. Curry leaves are known by various names in different languages: "Karivempu" in Tamil, "Barsunga" in Bengali, and "Kurrypatte" in Hindi. It includes over 150 genera and 1,600 species [2]. Curry leaves are a common leaf-spice that is used in minimal amounts for fragrance because of the composition of volatile oil and improve digestion. The leaves taste slightly pungent, a bitter and feebly acidic, and they do not lose their flavour and

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qualities even from being dried. Curry leaf also used in several Indian ayurvedic and unani prescription.[3]

Cultivation and Collection:

The flowering is from mid-April to mid-May. Thus, under Sanwara (H. P.) conditions, the flowering peak was recorded in the last week of April. Their fruiting season ranged between mid July and end of August. But peak fruiting season to last week of July to 1st week of August. It posses/small black shiny berries or its fruits are edibles but their seeds are poisonous. Curry leaf is native to India and is a large shrub or small tree with fragrant, pinnate leaves. These leaves are commonly used in South Indian cuisine to enrich the flavor of curries and other preparations. It does best with full sun, but tolerates light shade as well. It will benefit from being fertilized to encourage strong leaf growth with palm or citrus fertilizer. In a well-drained potting mix, this plant does well in containers. It's capable of being grown outdoors in the likes of Southern California, South Texas and South Florida, but must be sheltered from freezing temperatures. Seeds are delicate, so be gentle with them. They are shipped in a wet peat moss/coir blend, and these should be planted as soon as they arrive.[4]

Taxonomic Classification Of Curry Leaves [5]:-

Kingdom - Plantae

Subkingdom- Tracheobionta

Superdivision - Spermatophyta

Division- Magnoliophyta

Class- Magnoliopsida

Subclass – Rosidae

Family- Rutaceae

Genus- *Murraya J. Koenig ex L.*

Species- *Murraya koenigii (L.) Spreng*

Origin And Varities:-

Curry leaf is native to India and ranges throughout almost the entire Indian subcontinent. It is found not only in India but also in Sri Lanka, and in several Southeast Asian countries, including Indonesia, Burma, Thailand, etc. In India the curry leaves are widely distributed in a range from Ravi to Sikkim and Assam and are very abundant in states like Bengal, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Kerala, Karnataka, Odisha and Andhra Pradesh. This wide distribution highlights the widespread cultivation and use of curry leaves across the region.[6] The curry leaf, originally native to India, is cultivated extensively across the country, including in the Himalayan regions. It is also found in Sri Lanka, Southeast Asia, and regions of the United States like California and Florida. [6]

Morphological characteristic: -

Morphological Characteristic	Description
Plant Type	Small, spreading shrub
Height	Up to 2.5 meters
Stem Colour	Dark green to brownish
Stem Diameter	About 16 cm
Bark	Longitudinally peeled revealing white wood underneath
Leaf Blade Length	About 30 cm
Leaflet Count	24 leaflets
Venation	Reticulate venation
Flower Colour	White
Flower Shape	Funnel-shaped
Flower Fragrance	Sweet, aromatic
Flower Diameter (Fully Opened)	1.12 cm
Flower Type	Bisexual
Fruit Shape	Oblong ovoid
Fruit Length	1.4 - 1.6 cm
Fruit Diameter	1 - 1.2 cm
Fruit Colour (Ripe)	Black and shiny
Pulp Colour	Wisteria blue
Seed Colour	Spinach green
Seed Length	About 11 mm
Seed Weight	445 mg

Phytochemistry [8]:-

Curry leaves (*Murraya koenigii*) a fragrant leaf used in Indian cooking. Apart from adding flavor to dishes, they are also known for their many healthy benefits. Curry leaves contain bioactive compounds that are the subject of study in phytochemistry. This therapeutic and nutritional potential is due to the presence of these compounds in the leaves.

Here Are Some Main Phytochemicals Found In Curry Leaves: -

Carotenoids: Carotenoids, such as beta-carotene, lutein, and zeaxanthin, are significant components of curry leaves. These compounds can help protect your eyes and reduce your risk of vision problems, and they also act as antioxidants to help protect

your body from damage. Beta-carotene is also good for skin and immune health.

Phenolic Compounds: Curry leaves are rich in the phenolic compounds quercetin, kaempferol and rutin. Compounds that are rich in antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and anti-microbial components, which are responsible for keeping your overall health along with preventing the body from several diseases.

Flavonoids: Flavonoids are another class of phytochemicals present in curry leaves. They include compounds like apigenin, myricetin, and luteolin. Flavonoids exhibit antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer activities.

Alkaloids: Alkaloids like murrayanine and mahanine are found in curry leaves. Alkaloids are associated with many pharmacological activities

like antimicrobial, antifungal, and anti-inflammatory effects.

Essential Oils : Curry leaves or curry leaf essential oil contains compounds like beta-caryophyllene, beta-pinene, and alpha-terpinene. These volatile compounds are responsible for the characteristic aroma and flavor of curry leaves.

Triterpenoids: Curry leaves also contain triterpenoids, including mahanimbin and koenimbin. These compounds have been studied for their potential antidiabetic and cholesterol-lowering effects.

Moisture	63.2%
Total Nitrogen	1.15%
Fats	6.15%
Total Sugars	18.92%
Starch	14.6%
Crude Fiber	6.8%
Ash	13.06%
Acid insoluble ash	1.35%

Carotenoids :-	
Lutein	9.744mg
d-tocopherol	18349
Total carotene	21.4mg/100mg
B-carotene	1.1mg/100g

Traditional Uses of M. Koenigii

The essential oils and powdered fresh leaves of *M. koenigii* have culinary application in seasoning dishes and for preparing ready to eat meals. Because of the strong antimicrobial activity of the oil obtained from leaves, its traditional uses include from a fragrance and flavoring agent. In the hair care process, fresh curry leaves are boiled with coconut oil until a black residue remains, which is used as a strong tonic that helps the natural coloring of the hair and strengthens it. Curry leaves, whole or in portions, have long been prized for their therapeutic properties as

antidepressants, blood purifiers, antifungals, and anti-diarrheal agents. [9-10-11]

Medicinal Uses of M. koenigii

M. koenigii possesses a variety of therapeutic properties. Various parts of the plant, including the leaves, roots, and bark, can be used to create tonics that aid digestion, relieve flatulence, or serve as antiemetics [12]. When the leaves are boiled, they develop a bitter taste and are effective in reducing fever. Additionally, the juice extracted from the root is used to alleviate renal pain [13]. *M. koenigii* leaves and roots are used for pain relief, piles treatment, reducing body heat and quenching thirst. They also help in relieving inflammation and itching and are particularly useful in treating blood disorders and leucoderma. Fresh green leaf can be helpful in treating dysentery, the leaf can also be boiled in milk and can be applied to make a paste which is useful to heal poisonous bites and eruptions in the skin.[14]

Microscopy and Macroscopy studies

The leaflets of *Murraya koenigii* L. Spreng are obliquely ovate, or slightly rhomboid, with an acuminate, obtuse, or acute apex. Its petiole is usually between 20 and 30 cm long. The leaves are reticulate venation pattern, dentate margin, asymmetrical base. Upon microscopic examination, one can see the presence of stomata on abaxial surface, but no stomata on adaxial surface. The stomata are found to be anomocytic type, which have a unique arrangement where greatly differentiated subsidiary cells are not present. In transverse section of the leaves, the epidermis consists of rectangular cells; it is also the outermost layer on the upper and lower sides of leaf. There is a cuticular layer covering the upper epidermis. In the midrib region, 1 to 4 layers of collenchymatous hypodermis supports the epidermis, and 2 to 5 layers of chlorenchyma cells filled with chlorophyll. The ground tissue includes oval to polygonal parenchyma cells, which are aligned with the vascular bundle.

Calcium oxalate is found in this region in the form of sandy and prismatic crystals.[15]

Pharmacological Activity Of *Murraya Koenigii*

Antimicrobial Activity

The antimicrobial activities of *Murraya koenigii* root hexane, methanol and chloroform extracts were evaluated against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi* and fungal strains (*Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans* and *Trichophyton rubrum*). The all three extracts showed activity against the tested pathogens, with the methanol extract exhibiting the most significant antimicrobial activity. It exhibited maximum inhibitory effect on *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Trichophyton rubrum*. All three extracts were effective against *Staphylococcus aureus*, and the aqueous extract of the root had no effect against the microorganisms.[16]

Hepatoprotective Active

The clinical practice of liver diseases.[17]

Anti-Inflammatory

Three solvents that were used for extraction of *Murraya koenigii* leaves were petroleum ether, chloroform and ethanol. The dose of 250mg/kg, which is equivalent to one-tenth of the lethal dose (LD50) of 2500mg/kg, was delivered to the rats by oral route. The antiinflammatory activity of the ethanolic extract was superior among the three extracts as indicated by the significant increase of

the paw edema induced by carrageenan in Wistar albino rats.[18]

Nephroprotective

Oral administration drink of aqueous extract of *Murraya koenigii* leaves on a daily basis for 30 days instreptozotocin induce diabetic in male rats were found significant reduction in serum urea and creatinine levels and promote tissue regeneration in kidney.[19]

Anticancer

Curry leaves have anti-mutagenic properties. They guard our bodies from various cancers. Curry leaves act as an anti-cancer agent due to flavonoids. They are known to block the growth of breast cancer cells. Curry leaves also prevent colon cancers in the body. Similarly, curry leaves also help in preventing the body from suffering from cervical cancer.[20]

Antioxidant Properties

Curry leaves are a very rich source of antioxidants like phenols and flavonoids which help protect the body from the harmful effects of free radicals and oxidative stress, thereby decreasing the risk of chronic diseases. This includes their antioxidant activity and their ability to fight tumors, research suggests, which may indirectly be linked to the bioactive compounds in curry leaves and their involvement in multiple biological processes.[21]

Antifungal Activity.

The antifungal property of *M. koenigii* has been described in several studies. In one example, the essential oil of the leaves was shown to have antifungal activity [22]. The bioactivity of *M. koenigii* leaves can be ascribed to the presence of phytochemical constituents having complex molecular structures and diverse action mechanisms (such as alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, phenolics, tannins and saponins), which are widely researched in terms of microbial and antifungal activity. Various studies affirm the traditional application of the plant as a fungus inhibitor. In vitro antifungal activity may support the use of curry leaves for the treatment of diarrhea, dysentery and eruptions in folklore ramacins [23]

Antidiabetic Activity

Alkaloids present in the leaves of *M. koenigii* have been explored and reported to have inhibitory effects on the aldose reductase enzyme, glucose utilization, and other enzyme systems for extending anti-diabetic effects [24]. *M. koenigii* was tested for the α -glucosidase inhibitory property and was found to inhibit α glycosidase. Alpha-glucosidase inhibitors are widely used in the treatment of patients with type 2 diabetes [25].

Wound healing

Wound healing is a unique, multi-step process that involves multiple biochemical and cellular mechanisms that ultimately restore functional and anatomical continuity. The leaves of *M. koenigii* significantly increased the contraction of wound and reduced the epithelialization time and promoted collagenation in male albino rats in the histopathological section of males rats suggest that it could accelerate wound healing. The evidence supporting wound healing potential of *M. koenigii* can be satisfactorily observed from these findings.[26]

Immunomodulatory Activity

The immune system creates a web and controls activities necessary for the well-being of a life form by preventing the penetration and intrusion of microbes. Infection The body's immune system can overact and can underact. Most of the immune deficiencies or diseases can be due to the dysfunction of the immune system, which leads to a spectrum of disorders such as chronic inflammation and cancer [27]. The extract of *M. koenigii* also shows promise as an immunomodulatory agent through stimulating humoral immunity and phagocytic function [28].

CONCLUSION: -

In conclusion, due to presence of the herb is packed with antioxidants, antibacterial and skin-rejuvenating properties, the concept of a curry leaf-based herbal face wash is very promising. The gentle, effective cleanse provided by curry leaves makes this formulation perfect for those looking for a natural, sustainable skincare solution. This product which is developed with caution, could meet the increasing need for plant based luxury eco-mazing beauty home care products, making it a popular choice for a skin health booster.

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